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اللَّهُمَّ اجْعَلْهُمُ
مِنْ رَحْمَتِكَ

Twitter: A powerful tool to Improve Research Visibility and Impact

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[@aalebrahim](https://twitter.com/aalebrahim)

www.researcherid.com/rid/C-2414-2009

<http://scholar.google.com/citations>

11th January 2017

All of my presentations are available online at:

https://figshare.com/authors/Nader_Ale_Ebrahim/100797

Link to this presentation: <https://dx.doi.org/10.6084/m9.figshare.4538783.v1> (New version)

4th SERIES OF INTRODUCTORY WORKSHOP ON: *Strategies to Enhance Research Visibility, Impact & Citations*

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www.researcherid.com/rid/C-2414-2009
<http://scholar.google.com/citations>

Read more:

1. Ale Ebrahim, N., Salehi, H., Embi, M. A., Habibi Tanha, F., Gholizadeh, H., Motahar, S. M., & Ordi, A. (2013). [Effective Strategies for Increasing Citation Frequency](#). *International Education Studies*, 6(11), 93-99. doi: 10.5539/ies.v6n11p93
2. Ale Ebrahim, Nader. ["Optimize Your Article for Search Engine."](#) *University of Malaya Research Bulletin* 2.1 (2014): 38-39.

Abstract

Abstract: There are statistically significant associations between higher citations for articles and the use of various social networking sites such as Twitter, Facebook, blogs and forums. Twitter is a microblogging tool and social media site created in 2006 that gives you a chance to share quick thoughts using not more than 140 characters in a post. It's a great way to share your current research, publications and links to achieve maximum publicity. Twitter assist you to stay current with the literature and new developments in your field of interest. Proper tools allow the researchers to increase the research impact and citations. This presentation will provide various techniques on how microblogging improving your research impact and visibility.

Keywords: H-index, Improve citations, Research tools, Bibliometrics, Twitter, Research visibility

WORKSHOP SERIES TOPICS

SESSION	DATE	TIME	TOPIC
1	7 September 2016	2.00 – 4.30 p.m.	Citations and its impact to university ranking
2.1	22 September 2016	10.00 a.m. – 12.00	Research Outreach: Wider Visibility to Increase Citation*
2.2		2.00 – 5.00 p.m.	Plain Language Summary: The Common Language of Research & Innovation *
3	28 September 2016	2.00 – 4.30 p.m.	Analysis of bibliometrics information for select the best field of study
4	5 October 2016	2.00 – 4.30 p.m.	A new system for measuring research impact
5	12 October 2016	2.00 – 4.30 p.m.	How to select a brand name for your research interest?

<http://umconference.um.edu.my/ws>

9	9 November 2016	2.00 – 4.30 p.m.	Create a google scholar profile to boost research visibility
10	16 November 2016	2.00 – 4.30 p.m.	Create and maintain an up-to-date researcherid profile
11	23 November 2016	2.00 – 4.30 p.m.	Online repository: improving the research visibility and impact
12	30 November 2016	2.00 – 4.30 p.m.	Kudos: promote your published research reach and impact
13	7 December 2016	2.00 – 4.30 p.m.	Journal selection procedure: select the best journal to ensure the highest citation
14	14 December 2016	2.00 – 4.30 p.m.	Establish your expertise with a science blog
15	21 December 2016	9.00 – 11.30 a.m.	Promote your research work on LinkedIn
16	4 January 2017	9.00 – 11.30 a.m.	Make your data discoverable on a data repository
17	11 January 2017	9.00 – 11.30 a.m.	Microblogging for enhancing the research accessibility
18	18 January 2017	9.00 – 11.30 a.m.	Make an audio slides for your research
19	25 January 2017	2.00 – 4.30 p.m.	Academic social networking (ResearchGate & Academia) and the research impact
20	15 February 2017	2.00 – 4.30 p.m.	Publish online magazine to promote publications and research findings
21	22 February 2017	2.00 – 4.30 p.m.	Enhance research visibility by tracking citations
22	1 March 2017	2.00 – 4.30 p.m.	“Document publishing tools” for research visibility improvement
23	8 March 2017	2.00 – 4.30 p.m.	Publication’s e-mail marketing procedure
24	15 March 2017	2.00 – 4.30 p.m.	The use of reference management tools to improve citation
25	22 March 2017	2.00 – 4.30 p.m.	Contribute to Wikipedia: an approach to increase research visibility on the web

Top 10 authors with the highest profile view counts on ResearchGate

Table 11. Top 10 authors with the highest profile view counts on ResearchGate (9th of November, 2015), compared to the same indicator on the 10th of September, 2015.

AUTHOR NAME	SEPTEMBER 10 th	NOVEMBER 9 th	MISMATCH (%)
	(2015) PROFILE VIEWS	(2015) PROFILE VIEW	
Nader Ale Ebrahim	19,821	13,281	67.00
Chaomei Chen	7,760	3,937	50.73
Loet Leydesdorff	4,227	1,758	41.59
Bakthavachalam Elango	2,883	1,756	60.91
Zaida Chinchilla	5,840	1,569	26.87
Mike Thelwall	4,297	1,568	36.49
Lutz Bornmann	3,129	1,439	45.99
Wolfgang Glänzel	3,012	1,301	43.19
Kevin Boyack	3,256	1,135	34.86
Peter Ingwersen	2,335	1,025	43.90

Source: Martín-Martín, A., Orduna-Malea, E., Ayllón, J. M., & López-Cózar, E. D. (2016). The counting house, measuring those who count: Presence of Bibliometrics, Scientometrics, Informetrics, Webometrics and Altmetrics in Google Scholar Citations, ResearcherID, ResearchGate, Mendeley, & Twitter. *EC3 Reseach Group: Evaluación de la Ciencia y de la Comunicación Científica Universidad de Granada and Universidad Politécnica de Valencia (Spain), In Progress*,. doi:10.13140/RG.2.1.4814.4402

Research Tools Mind Map

Research Tools -> (4) Research Tools -> Networking -> Microblogging

lar@ VPS @iaravps · Mar 12

@skonkiel You can even cite what you didn't read, but you can't cite what you don't know exists :)

1

1

Picture credit to: [Scott Gelber](#)

Source: http://www.nytimes.com/2016/03/13/opinion/sunday/should-all-research-papers-be-free.html?_r=0

The Value and how-tos of Blogging and Microblogging for disseminating your research

Blogs and microblogs (e.g. Twitter) are vital tools for academics to publicly communicate about research developments and findings, to announce publications and share presentations and to write about relevant research issues. You can also gain feedback from other like-minded academics, as well as expand your networks and enhance your visibility.

Increased visibility online helps your offline recognition. Readers of your blog and microblogs learn more about who you are as a person, and as a researcher and professional. As a result, you may even be offered new academic and professional opportunities, including offers to give presentations or speeches and invitations to contribute blog posts or articles to various online or offline publications.

In short, blogging and microblogging greatly supplement the offline methods of research dissemination and networking. They are critical online methods for communicating and engaging with a massive global network of researchers and peers.

Source: http://www.elsevier.com/_data/assets/pdf_file/0015/145050/ECR_Blogging_210912.pdf

[PLoS One](#). 2016 Dec 1;11(12):e0165997. doi: 10.1371/journal.pone.0165997. eCollection 2016.

Bibliographic Analysis of Nature Based on Twitter and Facebook Altmetrics Data.

[Xia F](#)¹, [Su X](#)¹, [Wang W](#)¹, [Zhang C](#)¹, [Ning Z](#)¹, [Lee I](#)².

Abstract

This paper presents a bibliographic analysis of Nature articles based on altmetrics. We assess the concern degree of social users on the Nature articles through the coverage analysis of Twitter and Facebook by publication year and discipline. The social media impact of a Nature article is examined by evaluating the mention rates on Twitter and on Facebook. Moreover, the correlation between tweets and citations is analyzed by publication year, discipline and Twitter user type to explore factors affecting the correlation. The results show that Twitter users have a higher concern degree on Nature articles than Facebook users, and Nature articles have higher and faster-growing impact on Twitter than on Facebook. **The results also show that tweets and citations are somewhat related, and they mostly measure different types of impact.** In addition, the correlation between tweets and citations highly depends on publication year, discipline and Twitter user type.

PMID: 27906981 DOI: [10.1371/journal.pone.0165997](https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0165997)

(a)

(b)

(c)

(d)

Source: Xia, F., Su, X., Wang, W., Zhang, C., Ning, Z., & Lee, I. (2016). Bibliographic Analysis of Nature Based on Twitter and Facebook Altmetrics Data. *PLOS ONE*, 11(12), e0165997.

Promote Your Publication

- *Be active on any social networking site that you might prefer (**Twitter**, Facebook, your subject area's community forums etc) and mention your publication there. Don't forget to add value to the information, e.g. post a link to the first chapter etc.*

Source: <http://www.springer.com/authors/book+authors?SGWID=0-154102-12-489999-0>

If I tweet will you cite?

Original Article

International Journal of Public Health

pp 1-8

First online: 18 May 2016

If I tweet will you cite? The effect of social media exposure of articles on downloads and citations

Thomy Tonia , Herman Van Oyen, Anke Berger, Christian Schindler, Nino Künzli

Article Metrics

Microblogging

Microblogging is the shorter form of blogging. The most popular microblogging site is Twitter. This form of social information sharing is also a brief and effective way to announce research and publications, as well as to attract attention to your website and blog. You can attach documents, images or videos to your microblogging posts.

Get started:

▶ Sign up for free with one of the popular microblogging tools, such as: *Twitter* or *Tumblr*. All you need is a username and password.

Twitter

Twitter gives you a chance to share quick thoughts, statements and announcements with followers, using no more than 140 characters. It is a great way to quickly share your current research, publications, opinions, questions, and links to new blog posts. You can follow other researchers and thereby increase your own following.

Microblogging

Nader Ale Ebrahim
@aleebrahim

Nader Ale Ebrahim PhD in Technology Management, Virtual R&D Teams expert and founder of "Research Tools" Box.
mindmeister.com/39583892/resea... papers.ssrn.com/sol3/cf_dev/Ab
...
Malaysia · aleebrahim.com

1,901 TWEETS 1,044 FOLLOWING 511 FOLLOWERS

[Edit profile](#)

Tweets

View Exposé
Messages (+4)
E-mail monitoring
Visitors
7890 since 01.08.2010

Edit Exposé information
Preferences

Id
Search Results
My text
My links

Save as document

Hello, **Nader Ale Ebrahim**

Nader Ale Ebrahim Arabic [Advanced Search](#)

[Like](#) 2 [Tweet](#) 1 [+1](#) 1

People Name Forename

Person-Info

 Nader Ale Ebrahim, 49, Technology Management @ University of Malaya (UM), Malaysia

▶ Add your personal slogan!

Homepage: aleebrahim.com

Country: Iran, Islamic Republic of, **Language:** English

I offer: Main research interests: - Virtual teams - Virtual R&D teams - Collaborative Systems - e-Collaboration - Collaborative system - R&D Management - SMEs - Stage-Gate - Conceptual Model of Virtual Product Development - New product development - Concurrent engineering

My rating
★★★★★ (31)

▶ Link/Domain for my Exposé
▶ Show my Exposé on Yasni front page
▶ Invitation status of contacts

37 Images of Nader Ale

1 - 9 from 37

Contacts of Nader Ale (39)

All Confirm (9) Unconfirmed (1) Business [...] Private [...]

July 2015 Top 100 Technology Experts to Follow on Twitter

	#71) @glebis - Gleb Kalinin	
	#72) @aleebrahim - Nader Ale Ebrahim	
	#73) @1001topwords - Anfossi Willy (Down from #41)	
	#74) @saivinod - Vinod Kumar	
	#75) @thomas_witt - Thomas Witt (Down from #66)	
	#76) @iselGermanyAG - isel Germany AG (Down from #72)	
	#77) @johanlouwers - Johan Louwers (Up from #79)	
	#78) @buhalis - ProfDimitriosBuhalis	

December 2016 Top 100 Technology Experts to Follow on Twitter

#16) @in

#17) @Ca
#16)

#18) @yc

#19) @aleebrahim - Nader Ale Ebrahim (#19 last month)

CONGRATS! YOU MADE THE TOP 100

TECHNOLOGY EXPERTS TO FOLLOW FOR DECEMBER 2016.

EVANCARMICHAEL.COM

Why should you share links to your published work online?

According to Dr Melissa Terras from the University College London Centre for Digital Humanities, “If you tell people about your research, they look at it. Your research will get looked at more than papers which are not promoted via social media” (2012).

- Digital Curiosities: Resource Creation Via Amateur Digitisation
- Enabled backchannel: conference Twitter use by digital humanists Not Me
- Framework for effective public digital records management in Uganda
- Library and information resources and users of digital resources in the huma
- A Virtual Tomb for Kelvingrove: Virtual Reality, Archaeology and Education
- What do faculty and students really think about e-books? Not me
- Documentation and the users of digital resources in the humanities
- Classification in British public libraries: a historical perspective Not me
- Teaching TEI: The Need for TEI by Example
- Should we just send a copy? Digitisation, Use and Usefulness

Effect of social networks (Twitter) on the impact and downloads of an open access paper deposited in a repository

ChartDirector (unregistered) from www.advsofteng.com

861 downloads within 24 hours of the first tweet about a paper

Who gives a tweet? After 24 hours and 860 downloads, we think quite a few actually do

Earlier this year, the National Centre for Research Methods released a research paper to waves of interest from academics and researchers alike on Twitter. **Kaisa Puustinen** and **Rosalind Edwards** watched the number of downloads rise rapidly as the paper was passed around through the social media channel.

Students, early career researchers and established academics may all ponder about how many interviews will be enough when designing their research projects. Sarah Elsie Baker from Middlesex University and Rosalind Edwards from NCRM decided to tackle this subject and

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Popular Posts This Week

861 downloads within 24 hours of the first tweet about a paper

- The paper was uploaded online late afternoon on Monday 26th March and was first tweeted to our followers the following day. The paper caught the interest of NCRM Twitter followers and within 24h it was retweeted 10 times to over 5000 followers and shared 135 times using social sharing tools (email, microblogging, social bookmarking, social networking) available on NCRM website. This resulted in 861 downloads within 24 hours of the first tweet about our paper. This was clearly a Twitter effect, as the paper was not publicised anywhere else at that time.

Nader Ale Ebrahim

@aleebrahim

#VirtualTeams : A Literature Review reach to 7,605 Abstract Views and 1,915 Downloads :: SSRN [papers.ssrn.com/sol3/papers.cf ...](http://papers.ssrn.com/sol3/papers.cf...)

9:33 AM - 17 May 2015

Paper statistics	
Abstract Views:	7,617
Downloads:	1,915
Download Rank:	4,187
References:	130

Virtual Teams: A Literature Review

Nader Ale Ebrahim

University of Malaya (UM) - Department of Engineering Design and Manufacture, Faculty of Engineering; University of Malaya (UM) - Research Support Unit, Centre of Research Services, Institute of Research Management and Monitoring (IPPP)

Shamsuddin Ahmed

University of Malaya (UM)

Zahari Taha

University of Malaya (UM)

November 6, 2009

Australian Journal of Basic and Applied Sciences, Vol. 3, No. 3, pp. 2653-2669, 2009

Abstract:

In the competitive market, virtual teams represent a growing response to the need for fast time-to-market, low-cost and rapid solutions to complex organizational problems. Virtual teams enable organizations to pool the talents and expertise of employees and non-employees by eliminating time and space barriers. Nowadays, companies are heavily investing in virtual team to enhance their performance and competitiveness. Despite virtual teams growing prevalence, relatively little is known about this new form of team. Hence the study offers an extensive literature review with definitions of virtual teams and a structured analysis of the present body of knowledge of virtual teams. First, we distinguish virtual teams from conventional teams, different types of virtual teams to identify where current knowledge applies. Second, we

Anthony J Olejniczak @AJolejniczak · Jul 30

Excellent, can't wait to see it published.

Brett @BrettButtiere

@rmounce here is correlations for the measures, paper is under review at scientometrics

osf.io/3hv4f/

Brett @BrettButtiere

Follow

@rmounce here is correlations for the measures, paper is under review at scientometrics

osf.io/3hy4f/

Approaching quality like intelligence or personality, Buttliere

14

Table 2: Correlations between variables that will be analyzed NOT FINAL VARIABLES (NAMES). Do like descripti

	1.	2.	3.	4.	5.	6.	7.	8.	9.	10.	11.	12.	13.	14.	15.	16.	17.
1. Crossref	1																
2. Pubmed	0.57	1															
3. Scopus	0.68	0.64	1														
4. PubMedCentralEurope	0.52	0.54	0.68	1													
5. Datasite	-0.01	-0.02	0.00	-0.01	1												
6. Full ViewCount	0.39	0.37	0.44	0.39	0.02	1											
7. PubMedCentralViews	0.39	0.38	0.45	0.39	-0.06	0.47	1										
8. Month ViewCount	0.24	0.24	0.32	0.27	0.02	0.69	0.41	1									
9. Views data on Figshare	-0.02	0.00	0.05	0.03	0.01	0.16	0.08	0.2	1								
10. Mendeley Saves	0.35	0.32	0.38	0.33	0.04	0.61	0.31	0.44	0.07	1							
11. F1000 Recommends	0.06	0.06	0.07	0.07	0.01	0.12	0.05	0.08	0.01	0.07	1						
12. List of articles	0.11	0.08	0.12	0.09	0.03	0.51	0.1	0.38	0.05	0.25	0.06	1					
13. Curated list of articles	0.07	0.05	0.09	0.06	0.02	0.42	0.07	0.31	0.05	0.19	0.07	0.82	1				
14. Wikipedia	0.04	0.03	0.05	0.03	0.01	0.18	0.00	0.13	0.07	0.1	0.04	0.21	0.21	1			
15. Wordpress	0.04	0.02	0.06	0.03	0.01	0.16	0.04	0.1	0.02	0.1	0.01	0.23	0.23	0.09	1		
16. Researchblogging	0.02	0.02	0.03	0.02	0.00	0.09	0.02	0.06	0.00	0.05	0.03	0.15	0.17	0.04	0.11	1	
17. Scienceseeker	0.01	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.02	0.00	0.01	0.00	0.01	0.00	0.05	0.05	0.02	0.03	0	1
18. Twitter	0.14	0.12	0.16	0.14	0.06	0.60	0.07	0.39	0.05	0.42	0.07	0.5	0.42	0.16	0.17	0.08	0
19. Facebook	0.02	0.00	0.04	0.02	0.02	0.30	0.06	0.25	0.03	0.15	0.01	0.36	0.30	0.10	0.08	0.05	0
20. Reddit	0.00	0.00	0.01	0.01	0.00	0.11	0.04	0.11	0.01	0.05	0.01	0.17	0.16	0.05	0.12	0.00	0
21. PLoS Comments	0.05	0.07	0.08	0.06	0.01	0.21	0.05	0.16	0.02	0.12	0.02	0.25	0.25	0.08	0.12	0.04	0

Anthony J Olejniczak @AJOlejniczak · Jul 30

Excellent, can't wait to see it published.

The screenshot shows a table of correlations between various measures. A red circle highlights a specific cell in the table, likely indicating a key correlation value mentioned in the tweet.

Brett @BrettButtiere

@rmounce here is correlations for the measures, paper is under review at scientometrics

osf.io/3hv4f/

Final paper 1.1.docx

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Download

View

Revisions

Filter

- Personalizing papers; comparing p...
- OSF Storage
- Final paper 1.1.docx**
- First colloquium3.0.pptx

Page: 1 of 35 Automatic Zoom

Approaching quality like intelligence or personality, Buttiere 1

Dear Editors,

Jürgen Buder and myself kindly request your consideration for publication our manuscript titled, "Examining latent factors in Altmetrics; comparing paper 'Quality' or 'Impact' to person 'Intelligence' and 'Personality.'" The goal of the article is to understand better what we are measuring with the common (alt)metrics, and then stimulating a discussion about whether this is actually what we want to measure.

The analysis utilizes psychometric tests, treating a scientific paper as an entity with traits, to examine how many latent traits 22 of the most common metrics indicate, and what metrics

The Online Academic

embracing social media & internet services to enhance your career

Twitter for Academics

A five-part guide to using Twitter as an academic:

PART ONE. **Nuts & Bolts**: Finding your way around the lingo and Twittersphere.

PART TWO. **The Talking Business Card**: The *Dos and Do Nots* of Twitter and effectively using Twitter as a talking business card.

PART THREE. **How to Start Tweeting**: Starting well and setting up a great account that will serve you for a long time.

PART FOUR. **Twelve Rules of Tweeting**: Learn from my mistakes, make up your own rules but take a look at mine first.

PART FIVE. **Growing Your Network**: How to connect with other users and stay connected.

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The Author

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Publishing Tips

How to improve the impact of your paper

By Manon Burger Posted on 14 September 2014

Twitter

Twitter gives you a chance to share quick thoughts using no more than 140 characters. Today, one third of all scholars are active on Twitter. It's a great way to share your current research, publications and links to new blog posts.

Make an impact:

- Make a profile on www.twitter.com
- Follow other researchers and thereby increase your own following
- Post regular content, e.g. links to hot papers, events and conferences
- Respond promptly to direct messages and comments
- Retweet. By promoting other members of your community you are raising your own profile at the same time
- Use images. A picture is twice as likely to be retweeted as text

Source: <http://www.elsevier.com/authors-update/story/publishing-tips/how-to-improve-the-impact-of-your-paper>

Find your community on Twitter

Twitter is a microblogging site with 560 million active users, and more than 1 in 40 researchers are reportedly active on the site.

Scientists who use Twitter tend to be effusive in their praise: Twitter helps them stay on top of news in their field, find new publications, get speaking and publishing opportunities, communicate their research directly to the public, and—perhaps most importantly—find a sense of community. In fact, among researchers who use social media in a professional context, 83% declared Twitter to be the most useful tool they use.

Find your community on Twitter

- **Sign up** - Creating a Twitter account is dead simple: logon to Twitter.com and sign up for an account.
- **Personalize your account** - First, add a photo to your “avatar”. Next, add a short bio.
- **Find people to follow** - Find users who share your interests and to “follow” them to start receiving their updates.

Source: <http://blog.impactstory.org/category/impact-challenge/page/3/>

Basics of composing a tweet

No matter what you tweet about, there are some basic things you can do to make your tweets more interesting to others (and thus more likely to be shared via a retweet):

- use hashtags (a word or phrase that follows the “#” sign, like “#scicomm” or “#tenure”)
- attach a photo to your tweet (when composing a tweet, click the “Add photo” camera icon and upload a picture from your computer),
- consider following the 5-3-2 rule: social media experts recommend that for every 10 updates you post, 5 should be content from others that are relevant to your followers, 3 should be professional content, and 2 should be personal updates

Hashtagify Find, Analyze, Amplify

Related HashTags | Top Influencers | Usage Patterns | Wall | Instagram Tracking **New!**

All-time Top 6 Influencers for #bibliometrics

1. LSEImpactBlog
2. GlobalHigherEd
3. Research_Voice
4. david_colquhoun
5. **aleebrahim**
6. library_connect

Need more influencers?

SHARE

Top Recent Media

Dan Holden
@danholden
The Impact Factor is the last refuge of a scoundrel #metrics #bibliometrics
6:10 PM - 4 Jan 2017

LSE Impact Blog
@LSEImpactBlog
The number behind the number: suggesting a truer measure of academic impact
ow.ly/40Rz304Vn7B #metrics #citations #bibliometrics
6:00 PM - 9 Jan 2017

Hashtagify Find, Analyze, Amplify

All-time Top 6 Influencers for #researchtools

Top Recent Media

WIN GALAXY S7 NOW!!!
 @giveawayzutton

TRAP = Timeliness, Relevancy, Authority, Purpose. Making sure that research sources are credible #NBPS #ResearchTools #UnConference
 4:37 AM - 10 Jan 2017

Mr. Mooring
 @TheManPrincipal

TRAP = Timeliness, Relevancy, Authority, Purpose. Making sure that research sources are credible #NBPS #R #InConference

RiteTag

RiteTag / by RiteKit

Search for hashtags

By keyword

Scheduling

Automation

#virtual

Hashtag Analytics

RiteTag Recommendation: Use this hashtag to get seen now.

Estimated Hourly Statistics

unique tweets
per hour

hashtag
exposure
per hour

retweets
per hour

tweets with
images
per hour

tweets with
links
per hour

tweets with
mentions
per hour

Graphs

Last 30 days

Measuring your success

- Twitter's new [Analytics dashboard](#) can help you measure the success of your outreach efforts.
- Logon to Twitter Analytics and review your latest tweets that share links to your blog or your papers.
- The number of **impressions** are time your tweets appeared on someone's timelines. The number of **engagements** are the number of times your tweets have been retweeted, clicked through, or clicked on to learn more information about what you shared. They help you measure the amount of exposure you're receiving and others' interest in what you're tweeting, respectively.

The Kardashian index: a measure of discrepant social media profile for scientists

$$F=43.3C^{0.32}(1)$$

Where F is the number of twitter followers and C is the number of citations.

As a typical number of followers can now be calculated using this formula, Hall (2014) proposed that the Kardashian Index

(K-index) can be calculated as follows:

$$K\text{-index}=F(a)/F(c)$$

Where $F_{(a)}$ is the actual number of twitter followers of researcher X and $F_{(c)}$ is the number researcher X should have given their citations. Hence a high K-index is a warning to the community that researcher X may have built their public profile on shaky foundations, while a very low K-index suggests that a scientist is being undervalued. Here, Hall (2014) proposed that those people whose K-index is greater than 5 can be considered 'Science Kardashians'

[Neil Hall, Prof](#)

Modified Kardashian Index: A Measure of Discrepant Social Media Profile for Scientists

$F(a)$ is the actual number of Twitter followers

$F(c)_m$ is the calculated social impact of the author based on the scientist Google Scholar citations (C_{Gs})

MK-index is Modified Kardashian index

$$F(c)_m = 43.3 (5.961 + 0.460C_{Gs})^{0.32}$$

$$\text{MK-index} = F(a)/F(c)_m$$

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